

An Approach to Exploit Compensatory Motions in Upper-Limb Prostheses Control

Maddalena Feder^{1,2}, Giorgio Grioli^{1,2}, Manuel G. Catalano¹ and Antonio Bicchi^{1,2}

Abstract—Among the recent investigations in upper-limb prostheses, the research still focuses on exploring new control solutions to reduce the user’s mental fatigue and improve the control’s robustness and intuitiveness. Some studies present solutions to close the control loop by using compensatory motions as error indexes. A previous relation is established to associate a predefined compensation motion to a given prosthetic degree of freedom. We developed an approach to avoid this step and directly correlate the human motions to as many prosthetic joints as needed. The implemented algorithm is tested in Simulink for a simulated trans-humeral amputee.

Index Terms—prosthetic control, compensatory motions, upper-limb amputation

I. INTRODUCTION

According to [1], in the United States, approximately 185,000 persons undergo an amputation of the upper or lower limb each year. Among the several reasons which cause amputations, we find diabetes, accidents, neurological disorders, and infections. Three different typologies of prostheses help people to continue to live their lives: passive/cosmetic, body-powered, and myoelectric prostheses [2]. In particular, this last typology is of great interest to the research field, which tries to investigate new control possibilities to avoid the passive use of the prosthesis and its final rejection [2]. [3] offers an overview of several control methods studied nowadays. Among these, the myoelectric signals from the stump muscles are widely tested with different control strategies, allowing the user to control the functioning of several degrees of freedom (DoF). As shown in [4], two electrodes are placed on the antagonist muscles of the residual stump to command the opening and closure of the hand. Many commercial hands [5] implement this control strategy. However, as soon as the number of degrees of actuation increases, additional electrodes are needed, as shown in [6], and less impulse signals can be exploited. Another drawback of this approach is how the skin affects the results, for instance, when the subject is sweating. Several studies explore alternative prosthetic control solutions, such as the one proposed in [7], which combines the signals obtained from the electrodes with the signals coming from additional sensors, like Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs). Nevertheless, the control of myoelectric prostheses can be tiresome or complex and leads prosthetic users to develop

undesired compensatory motion habits, that in turn can lead to postural issues and chronic pain. [8] exploits those compensatory motions performed by the prosthetic users as error indexes to close the control loop. In this way, the human is not in charge of controlling the prosthesis but is the prosthesis itself, which by moving, corrects the human posture by leading it back to the target position. In [9] and [10], the control of two DoF, wrist pronosupination and elbow flexion/extension, is studied. Additionally, [8] highlights that to supplant wrist pronosupination, amputated subjects tend to use trunk and arm compensatory motions to change hand-orientation.

We try to avoid this a priori correlation between compensatory and prosthetic arm movements by proposing a novel control strategy for upper-limb prostheses, adaptable to a greater number of prosthetic DoF. We test in simulation this approach, by comparing the functioning with and without the prosthetic controller.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

Consider a prosthetic user and define \dot{x}_e as their end-effector velocity. Define \dot{q}_h and \dot{q}_p as the vectors of the human’s and prosthesis’ joints velocities, and identify J_{he} and J_{pe} the Jacobian matrices of the human and prosthetic components, respectively. The general formula for the end-effector differential kinematics is

$$\dot{x}_e = [J_{he} \quad J_{pe}] \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_h \\ \dot{q}_p \end{bmatrix} \approx k_e (x_d - x_e), \quad (1)$$

where the last term of the equation, $k_e (x_d - x_e)$, would be a desirable control to make the error $x_d - x_e$ converge to zero thanks to a gain k_e .

To avoid any previous correlations between compensatory and missing limb motions, we introduce a second kinematic task to converge the position of a target frame \tilde{x}_C to zero, as

$$\dot{x}_C = [J_{hc} \quad J_{pc}] \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_h \\ \dot{q}_p \end{bmatrix} \approx k_C (\tilde{x}_C - x_C), \quad (2)$$

where \dot{x}_C is the compensatory target frame velocity, J_{hc} and J_{pc} the Jacobian matrices for human and prosthesis for the compensation task, k_C is a gain and \tilde{x}_C and x_C the target and actual compensatory frame positions. J_{pc} is considered null.

Starting from Equations (1) and (2), we propose an approach in which the human is in charge of the task reaching and she/he moves as the prosthetic joints were stopped. We assume that the human tries to execute the reaching task.

$$\dot{q}_h = J_{he}^\dagger k_e (x_d - x_e). \quad (3)$$

This work was supported by the European Research Council Synergy Grant Natural BionicS (NBS) project (Grant Agreement No. 810346).

¹Soft Robotics for Human Cooperation and Rehabilitation, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova 16163, Italy (maddalena.feder@iit.it).

²Department of Information Engineering and Centro di Ricerca “Enrico Piaggio”, University of Pisa, 56122, Pisa, Italy.

Fig. 1. Simulated human model without (first row) and with (second row) prosthetic controller at different instants of time. The prosthetic arm is highlighted in purple. The desired end-effector position, x_d , is in meters equal to: $[0.4, -0.3, 0.2]$, while the orientation in roll-pitch-yaw is equal to $[1, 0, 1.3]$, specified in radians. The elbow angle is already set to 1.57 radians for the home pose.

Let's substitute Equation (3) in Equation (4), which describes the actual end-effector velocity as the contribution given both from the human and prosthesis:

$$\dot{x}_e = J_{he}\dot{q}_h + J_{pe}\dot{q}_p \quad (4)$$

Thereafter, we can include the compensatory task. We consider \dot{q}_p as the unknown variable, which is calculated as final step. It depends only on the joint values and on the compensation error, $\tilde{x}_C - x_C$. Therefore, the prosthesis changes the actual hand pose and the human adjusts her/his posture. At the end, both the compensatory and the reaching tasks will be solved.

III. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

The experiments have been tested in Matlab Simulink, where a human model with trunk and right arm is uploaded into the simulation. Fig. 1 reports the simulation at different instants of time for the considered trans-humeral amputee, starting from the home configuration (Fig. 1a) at $t = 0s$ to the final configuration (Fig. 1e) at $t = 5s$. The purple color identifies the prosthetic arm, with three DoF for the wrist and the additional elbow flexion/extension. The red point represents the desired end-effector pose, x_d , while the cyan point the target compensatory frame, \tilde{x}_C , chosen at the upper-arm frame. The same simulation has been repeated twice, to prove the effectiveness of the implemented controller in exploiting the performed compensatory motions to generate prosthetic joint velocity outputs. The first row of Fig. 1 refers to how the human behaves without the prosthesis controller, while in the second line the prosthesis controller is activated. As we can see, when the prosthesis controller is disabled, the prosthetic arm remains stationary, and the human compensates to reach the final end-effector pose. In the second case, the controller makes the prosthetic joints move as soon as the human compensatory motions are perceived. In this way, the user can go to the initial posture by charging the prosthesis in computing the reaching task.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, a novel control approach is offered for upper-limb prostheses in executing reaching task. No previous correlation between the body compensations and the missing limb motions is required. The performed simulations show the capability of this approach to adapt to a greater number of prosthetic DoF compared to the ones presented in the past researches. Further developments include the possibility to test this control strategy with real subjects and for different amputation levels.

REFERENCES

- [1] Terrence P. Sheedan, "9 - Rehabilitation and Prosthetic Restoration in Upper Limb Amputation" in Braddom's Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, 6th ed., David X. Cifu, Ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier000, 2021, 153-173.e2.
- [2] Sebastian Farr et al., "Peromelia - Congenital transverse deficiency of the upper limb: A literature review and current prosthetic treatment", in Journal of Children's Orthopaedics, 2018, pp. 1-8.
- [3] Alix Chadwell et al., "The Reality of Myoelectric Prostheses: Understanding What Makes These Devices Difficult for Some Users to Control", in Frontiers in Neurobotics, vol. 10, 2016.
- [4] Nawadita Parajulli et al., "Real-Time EMG Based Pattern Recognition Control for Hand Prostheses: A Review on Existing Methods, Challenges and Future Implementation", in Sensors vol. 19, Oct. 2019, p. 4596.
- [5] Cristina Piazza et al., "A Century of Robotic Hands", in Annual Review of Control, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems 2.1, 2019, pp. 1-32.
- [6] Cosimo della Santina et al., "Toward Dexterous Manipulation With Augmented Adaptive Synergies: The Pisa/IIT SoftHand 2", in IEEE Transactions on Robotics, vol. 34, n 5., 2018.
- [7] Michele Maimeri et al., "Design and Assessment of Control Maps for Multi-Channel sEMG-Driven Prostheses and Supernumerary Limbs", in Frontiers in Neurobotics, vol. 3, 2019.
- [8] Mathilde Legrand et al., "Controlling upper-limb prostheses with body compensations", in Wearable Robotics: Challenges and Trends, 2022.
- [9] M. Merad et al., "Assessment of an automatic prosthetic elbow control strategy using residual limb motion for transhumeral amputated individuals with socket or osseointegrated prostheses", in IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics, vol. 2, February 2020, pp. 38-49.
- [10] Mathilde Legrand et al., "A closed-loop and ergonomic control for prosthetic wrist rotation", in IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, May 2020, pp. 2763-2769.